

**ON THE CREATION OF EDUCATIONAL
CONTENT AND THE PECULIARITY OF
ITS USE FOR MISCELLANEOUS
LEARNING IN THE LESSONS OF THE
UZBEK LANGUAGE**

Education

Keywords: Mixed education, Uzbek language, digital technologies, interactive exercises, interactive dictator, “Savodxon”.

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Abstract

The article discusses the principles, stages, and methods of organizing Uzbek language classes on a mixed basis. The peculiarities of creating and using Uzbek language content for mixed education are explored in some of the issues of integrating traditional education and e-learning. The conclusion provides an overview of the challenges of implementing a mixed education approach and outlines the ways in which this education can be effectively developed.

Based on the Strategy for the Development of the State and Society in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Concept for the Development of Higher Education until 2030, the priority areas chosen by the educational institution in which we operate, the program of targeted actions, in conditions that include being in the forefront of reforms, teachers draw special attention to the integration of traditional and modern teaching methods. In this regard, the process of teaching the Uzbek language is no exception. On the contrary, at a time when the status of the Uzbek language as a state language is increasing, a natural process is to further increase attention to its development and improve its teaching methods.

According to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On measures to radically increase the prestige and status of the Uzbek language as the state language” of October 21, 2019 – October 21, 2019 is the day when, a bright and invaluable product of centuries-old culture, scientific, educational and artistic thinking, intellectual potential – the Uzbek language was given the status of the state language, declared the “Day of the Uzbek language”, a department for the development of the State language was organized under the Cabinet of Ministers. Along with the implementation of work aimed at the full and proper use of the possibilities of the state language in all areas of public life of the state, including in public administration, modern and innovative technologies, industry, the banking and financial system, law, diplomacy, military affairs, medicine and in other areas, it is necessary to note such designated functions as information and communication technologies of the state language, in particular, ensuring a worthy place in the world of information Discount Internet, the creation of computer programs of the Uzbek language and the development and implementation of a large scale, the Uzbek language textbooks for the local population and foreign nationals [1].

In this regard, in educational institutions, the issues of teaching the Uzbek language as a state language are even more relevant. By the way, the professional suitability and skill of a future specialist in the modern period include knowledge and application of terms used within their field, office work skills, the basics of speech culture and public speaking norms in the state language.

Along with this, the status of the teacher of the Uzbek language is fundamentally changing. Now he cannot fulfill the function of the sole source of information and the role of the supreme judge of the lesson. Now its functions are associated with the organization and support of students' independent education, coming into contact with them, as well as with the joint conduct of public project work with students. Secondly, the teacher of the Uzbek language is required to have pedagogical design skills, sufficient computer literacy. Although the Concept of Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 provides for the implementation of some measures to introduce digital technology and modern methods into the educational process, among them the following is continuously associated with the activities of professors and teachers:

Individualization of educational processes based on digital technologies, development of distance education services, widespread introduction of webinar, online, “blended learning”, “flipped classroom” technologies into practice;

Acceleration of the creation of national electronic educational resources, organization of work on the transfer of foreign electronic educational resources, a phased increase in the load of electronic resources in the educational process, the creation of electronic educational literature, in order to download them to mobile devices, create a system for placing information about electronic resources in libraries using QR-code;

Based on educational trends and specialties, the development of the use of modern traditional products, widely used internationally in the educational process [2].

It is known that the performance of these functions is continuously associated with the study of innovations taking place in the global educational industry. Indeed, the world experience, even without deep checks, only during a superficial study showed a number of their advantages. So, it is clear to everyone that it is unnecessary to argue about computer technology, in particular, about the incomparable role of e-education in the field of language teaching. It is not necessary to consider that the use of a computer in language training is just a tradition, but, on the contrary, it is necessary to take into account the need to promote the use of computer technologies in this process [3].

It is known that at the beginning most teachers had concerns when the concepts of an electronic textbook and an electronic teacher appeared in the educational process. The reason for this was the possibility of underestimating the role of the teacher in the lesson, or it was believed that he could only fulfill the function of manager.

Moreover, today there is a great demand for teacher intervention for the educational process through electronic textbooks, electronic resources, and this demand proves that such an opinion is absolutely wrong. Therefore, e-learning provides for the harmony of E-learning with traditional.

In the world educational system, the end of the 20th - beginning of the 21st centuries will become original by the appearance of new terms. In particular, the terms **edtech (educational technology)**, **e-learning (e-education)**, **miscellaneous-learning (miscellaneous learning)** are inextricably linked with our life. Development, from electronic textbooks to distance learning, cloud technology, and massive open online courses has become a factor for improving educational forms [4].

It is known that educational forms - (in Latin form - appearance) - is the cover for the educational process, its essence, logic and content. The following main forms of learning are available: traditional learning - *yuma-yuz* - face to face, face to face learning; *masofaviy o'qitish* – distance education, distance learning; *ochiq o'quv kurslari* – open learning, open learning; *moslashuvchan o'qitish* – flexible learning, Flexible learning; *aralash o'qitish* (talim) – miscellaneous learning, miscellaneous learning; *elektron o'qitish* (talim) – E-learning.

In our practice, in teaching the Uzbek language, just like in the methodology of other subjects, we see a type of traditional education harmonized with distance education, that is, the result of blended learning.

Declan Byrne writes about the traditional “miscellaneous learning” (miscellaneous learning) as follows: This term refers to several learning methods that include learning outcomes and at the same time is used to describe learning that contains various types of activities relevant to electronic and independent learning [5]. In general, blended learning is aimed at the effective use of rich pedagogical experience and its symbol is manifested in the correct choice and harmonization of information and communication training tools, that is, digital technologies to achieve high results with low costs.

In this system, the teacher remains in the educational center and makes extensive and productive use of the Internet. Blended learning Distance education, consists of classroom learning (Face-to-Face learning) and online learning (Online learning).

The main principles introduced in the Uzbek language classes of blended learning consists of the following: a link to accurate and theoretical information; the interaction of students and trainers; transparency of training. The stages of introducing blended learning for classes in the Uzbek language are reflected in the following order: 1. Preparation of training material appropriate for the topic under study in a compact form, compilation of interactive exercises and tasks, interactive dictations for practical training, their publication in print or the creation of unlimited electronic educational publications and electronic sources for language training and their introduction into the educational process, including including: a) training programs with educational materials divided into modules; b) electronic educational publications that help to strengthen the rules of spelling and punctuation; c) training programs, including the rules of syntax and punctuation of the Uzbek language; d) electronic dictionaries: electronic spelling dictionary, electronic explanatory dictionary, electronic dictionaries of synonyms, homonyms, antonyms, phraseological units, figurative expressions; e) interactive exercises and dictations in the Uzbek

language; f) a program for creating tests; g) spreadsheets in the Uzbek language; h) educational audio programs, etc.

2. Presentation of texts using multimedia (text, voice, live movement, graphic image: tables, algorithms)
3. Provide instruction in the study of the submitted materials.
4. Self-study of materials submitted by students.
5. Organization of joint work of students in the classroom according to the established schedule of lessons on textbooks and teaching aids, fiction and scientific literature, electronic resources.
6. Fulfillment of curricula and case studies.
7. Organization and evaluation of tests on the topics studied.

In the implementation of blended learning, it is planned to provide students with the opportunity to express their opinions, to awaken self-confidence and motivation for students to study, to organize the help of more capable students to poor students, to provide students with a chance to correct a low grade.

How is blended learning implemented in the lessons of the Uzbek language? It is known that the Uzbek language is considered an applied science. Based on the scientific program created according to the communicative-cognitive approach, students have prepared speech topics and training programs in Uzbek grammar and, without requiring re-recording, reproductive and interactive exercises based on a partial search. They are compiled in the *Savodxon* multimedia application.

The blended learning we represent provides assistance to the traditional educational process and serves as a support for it. Uzbek language lessons are organized in classrooms, according to the lesson schedule established in the traditional way. Here, students receive methodological instructions on the subject, additional and basic literature, as well as on works involving the use of electronic sources and independent performance. At the end of the semester, the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities are evaluated in the traditional way. Along with this, students use educational materials on the subject “Uzbek language”, located in the Institute’s IP system (213.230.91.135).

Students will familiarize themselves with additional information on the topic being studied and submit certain tests on the online system. We do not provide for the education of all students on the Internet, almost without visiting the institute. There is an exception only for distance students. They will learn most of the topics by contacting the teacher on the Internet through chat rooms, forums, email address and instant messengers. The teaching materials on the Uzbek language to these students is represented by a hyperlink to texts, audio texts, videos, various tables, diagrams, photographs and sources. Correspondence students are also provided with electronic educational publications “Learning the rules of spelling”, “Learning the rules of punctuation”, the mobile application “*Savodxon*” as additional sources. The knowledge, skills and

abilities of students are controlled in such forms as performing interactive exercises and dictations, composing texts, writing E-mails. The process of exchanging information is carried out by sending and receiving files. And the assessment of the work performed is noted by recommendations and comments on the quality and accuracy of the work performed and the assessment for the work.

In the organization of blended learning, the *Savodxon* mobile application is of particular importance. This application is intended for use in lessons and extracurricular classes in the Uzbek language for the organization of independent training for students of groups with Karakalpak, Kazakh, Turkmen languages for teaching undergraduate universities. The task of the mobile application is to simplify the process of reinforcing a new topic through the use of interactive exercises and interactive dictations on speech and grammar topics studied within the subject, automation in the lessons of teachers and students' practical activities, control and quick, fair assessment of students' knowledge, skills and abilities.

Users of the *Savodxon* mobile application can voluntarily choose a module, go to exercises, evaluate their abilities by performing them, get familiar with the results of an automated assessment, take a screenshot of the results and send them to the teacher for the subject or group members. The application serves to increase interest in the subject among students, as well as to save teachers time and achieve high results without spending a lot of time and effort. In it, in a form convenient for students' self-control, only 150 interactive exercises and dictations for 15 modules, 10 exercises and dictations for each module are placed (Figure 1). 10 exercises of each module are composed from simple to complex and include various types of interactive dictations. Traditional dictations as a dictionary dictation, selective dictation, explanatory dictation, self-dictation, graphic dictation, translation dictation are transformed into interactive dictations.

Figure 1. Savodxon mobile application: cover, sections, modules, exercises.

After completing the tasks on your own at home, set in this mobile application, full-time students in the audience analyze interactive exercises and dictations by automated assessment (face-to-face sessions). In this process, students conduct individual, group, and joint activities. Taking into account the fact that this process, especially at the initial stage of introducing blended learning, requires more time and energy from the teacher in relation to the traditional lesson, it will be advisable if students with excellent and good academic performance serve as an assistant. According to this method, classroom work will be devoted to the analysis of the theoretical part of

a complex speech and grammar topic and answers to students' questions in the process of homework. Thus, the lesson will be a transition from teacher excellence to student priority.

Classes based on blended learning are divided into three parts: Introductory part, main part and final part.

The introductory part is organized on the basis of homework on a previously studied topic (educational tasks on a modular system, published in print and electronic literature), communication between the teacher and students. Students prepare to learn a new topic.

In the main part, the pronunciation and spelling of dialogues, new words and names are taught based on assignments, texts and audio and video materials, drawings on a new topic being studied.

In the final part, you can evaluate the work of students in small groups and ask problem tasks to arouse interest in the next topic. When evaluating, transparency and fairness are ensured, the group monitors the performance of their own and others' performance, receives the results of an automated assessment, evaluates each other.

In the Uzbek language classes based on blended learning, under the supervision of a teacher, students try to show interesting and controversial aspects of the topic; to solve lexical and grammatical problems, they additionally turn to linguistic and encyclopedic dictionaries. Thus, students will take the habit of searching, selecting and processing information to complete the assignment of the teacher. If they cannot find the recommended sources, then send their email addresses in order to download training materials in HTML, DOC, AVI, MP3 formats. That is, communication with the teacher will be constantly maintained.

After class, students at home finish practical work on a new topic, perform several more interactive exercises and dictations to strengthen the topic. At the same time, students continue to communicate not with the teacher, but with each other. In online communication, it is possible to receive answers to questions as soon as possible. In general, when introducing blended learning into the process of learning the Uzbek language, extreme flexibility and convenient resources of this training are observed.

At the beginning of the new school year, communication between the teacher and students in the Uzbek language begins in the audience and on-line and offline systems: students, along with a list of traditional literature mentioned in the curriculum, receive electronic literature and educational websites, as well as information about logins, passwords and instant messengers .

In the process of introducing blended learning in the Uzbek language lessons, the following positive aspects are observed: students have an increased desire to acquire the necessary knowledge, skills and abilities; the creative potential of the learner and students is increased; the possibility of regularly receiving information about the achievements and shortcomings of

students is increasing; in accordance with the purpose and objectives of the subject, with the specific capabilities and needs of students, the selection of teaching methods and learning tools convenient for managing the educational process is carried out; taking into account the needs of students, certain features, harmonization and improvement of traditional, interactive teaching methods is carried out; methodological support for the discipline is regularly updated; the professional competence of the teacher for the organization of blended learning is increasing.

Of course, in the process of blended learning there are controversial and debatable issues. In particular, most professors and teachers have a dilemma in relation to educational news. As you know, in the methodology of teaching other subjects, there is a great possibility of using the best teaching tools, educational contents translated into Uzbek, and for blended learning the teacher of the Uzbek language is forced to create educational content himself. And this requires special preparation and time. For this reason, most teachers prefer traditional learning rather than blended learning. The lack of formation of skills of independent learning among students, their unpreparedness to overcome certain difficulties and failures negatively affects the effectiveness of blended learning. And also, the fact that in the first place is the issue of daily attendance in educational institutions does not increase the importance of distance learning.

Despite this, we believe that, in all universities of Uzbekistan, where the Uzbek language is studied as the state language, there are certain pedagogical conditions for the effective development of blended learning. Today, more and more representatives of the young generation who have great potential for communicating with technology and the use of digital technologies. Lack of harmonization of Uzbek language teaching and digital technology can lead to very large losses.

In the period of globalization around the world there is a demand for graduates who have received education through the method of blended learning or online. The reason for this is that such personnel are distinguished not only by knowledge in their specialty, but also by functional literacy, the ability to make independent decisions, and to conduct individual and joint activities. Of course, the introduction, which, despite a short 20-year history, has high prestige, blended learning will become a factor in the effectiveness of teaching the Uzbek language. And also, he will change the teacher's task in the structure of education, gives him the role of a guide, instructing the Uzbek language in the world. So, unlike traditional teaching, in the organization of the Uzbek language lessons through blended learning, the main goal is not to teach students the Uzbek language, but to learn to listen, speak, write and read in the Uzbek language.

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